

Enhance driver behaviour & Public Acceptance
of Connected & Autonomous vehicles

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List of acronyms

Acronym	Meaning
VRU	Vulnerable Road Users
CCAM	Connected, Automated and Cooperative Mobility
G2A	Guide to Autonomy

Notice

This document partly complies with the European Blind Union’s guidelines on “Making information accessible for all”, available at <http://www.euroblind.org/publications-and-resources/making-information-accessible-all>).

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Executive summary

This document gives an overview of the technical settings of the Guide2Autonomy (G2A), which includes:

- the toolbox itself, which will include all the recommendations and guidelines developed, based on the project results and additional sources,
- a chatbot function, which will assist vulnerable users to find the recommendation they are looking for,
- a self-assessment tool (powered by Cross Skill®, which will assess the expertise level of connected and automated vehicle (CAV) service providers and help them guide through the toolbox of recommendations.

Target groups of the G2A are:

- Public authorities, local, national or European,
- Researchers, scientists and academics,
- Service providers in the field of CAVs and related services,
- Product developers, producing hardware and/or software,
- Citizen representatives, especially representing Vulnerable Road Users.

The other dimensions of the G2A, are CAV topic areas, impact areas and tool types, which will be accessible as filters in the toolbox and allow user to narrow down the result set of the recommendations they are looking for.

The toolbox is accessible by using the following link: www.guide2autonomy.eu.

The toolbox will be filled in with approximately 100 recommendations and guidelines by the involved partners of WP8 in the following months. The toolbox filled with the recommendations is part of the deliverable 8.3, which is due in Month 41.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and organization of the document

The main aim of the PASCAL project is to develop the “Guide2Autonomy” (G2A). Its purpose is to accelerate a user-oriented integration of connected cooperative and automated vehicles in our present transport systems. It will address all relationships between humans and the overall Connected Autonomous Vehicles (CAV) innovations, ranging from user orientation in HMI development. Human control in the frame of CAV driving simulations and demonstrations, user perceptions in relation to CAV services, acceptance as well as needs of training for CAVs by present and future “drivers”, up to wiliness of use and wiliness to pay.

This document shortly describes the structure (Chapter 2) and target groups (Chapter 3) of the G2A. The G2A itself can be found at www.guide2autonomy.eu. The G2A as well as two of the functionalities to access the G2A will be embedded in the Pascal project website www.pascal-project.eu

1.2 Intended audience of this document

The audience of this document is composed off the project partners, and more specifically WP- and Task-leaders as they will be writing the recommendations of the G2A.

2 Overall framework of the G2A

The Guide2Autonomy (G2A) and its recommendations will provide the different CAV stakeholders the means to increase awareness and user acceptance of CAVs. The G2A is set up as open access and data platform which will bring together all learnings and recommendations of the PASCAL project, and beyond for an improved awareness and acceptance of CAVs. These recommendations are aimed at a diverse range of CAV stakeholders.

Through its G2A, PAsCAL will deliver the wider CAV community with for example:

1. Learnings based on a thorough assessment of awareness, user and wider public acceptance of higher levels of connectivity and automation;
2. Guidelines on how to optimise usage of connected and automated solutions for both drivers and current non-drivers, including vulnerable users;
3. A framework of impacts and CAV topics that help to design, implement and monitor the awareness and acceptance of CAV technologies and services in the wider mobility system.
4. Tools for measurement of acceptance and awareness and improved inclusion of CAVs in the transport network,

Over 100 recommendations build upon lessons learned and experimentations of the PASCAL project, yet also from the PASCAL sister projects will constitute the core of the G2A content.

These recommendations will be made accessible through an online open access database that can be accessed through three different points of entry:

1. Browsing through recommendations with the help of a multi-criteria search function integrated within a G2A database functionality;
2. Specifically aimed at CAV service providers the access to the recommendations will be provided measured through an online self-assessment functionality (Cross Skill). This self-assessment will allow them to get specific access to the recommendations in relation to their level of awareness and proficiency in relation to CAVs.
3. A chatbot functionality will allow for a more accessible usage of the G2A by vulnerable user groups. It will allow for browsing the G2A contents through open requests. This chatbot will particularly aim at creating access to visually impaired users.

In the following paragraphs, the different functionalities will be shortly presented.

2.1 Accessing the Guide2Autonomy

The Guide2autonomy toolbox is available at www.guide2autonomy.eu.

Figure 2-1 Overview of the access to G2A

In the last year of the project, the toolbox will be filled with the G2A recommendations and guidelines. The G2A consists of a toolbox (structured database), self-assessment tool and a chatbot. The different elements are described in the following paragraphs.

2.2 G2A toolbox

The core of the G2A is a WordPress data base. The following categorisation and characteristics of each recommendation structure the database:

- The user group(s) addressed by each recommendation (4 user types).
- The key thematic area of the recommendation (5 thematic areas).
- The expected level of impact of the recommendation (3 impact levels).
- The type of tool of the recommendation (three tool types).

Figure 2-2 Browsing criteria

The WordPress set up allows for changes if proven necessary during the development of the recommendations during the coming year.

2.3 G2A chatbot

The chatbot allows the identified G2A target group in finding the right tool/recommendation for their needs. The target group of users of the chatbot are vulnerable users, especially focused on blind and visually impaired users of the G2A. Since the chatbot, including the portal, allow the content manager to see the point of interests within the conversations, this target group could be extended in the future.

The chatbot functionality will be integrated in the PAsCAL project website. It will have also a speech to text and text to speech functionality. The

chatbot will be available in English. On the PAsCAL website, a chatbot icon is present on the bottom right (see Figure 2-3). While clicking on the icon, a chatbot will pop-up in view and allow the user to interact (see Figure 2-4). It has the advantage to increase the visibility of the chatbot and at the same time the visibility of the G2A.

Figure 2-3 Chatbot icon on the bottom right of the PAsCAL website

Figure 2-4 Chatbot pop-up on the G2A page

The chatbot portal will synchronise data published on the WordPress platform and retrieves the corresponding list of recommendations. Using that list, it will then synchronise its internal state with questions and answers and publish these to Microsoft’s QnAMaker to be able to recognize questions based on the provided set.

Figure 2-5 Chatbot portal and WordPress syncing

Data received from the WordPress is in a json format and contains bot specific information about each recommendation: direct link, questions and answers.

```

[
  {
    "url": "https://url/recommandation-1",
    "questions":[
      "Question 1?",
      "Question 2?",
      ...
    ],
    "answers":[
      "Answer 1",
      "Answer 2",
      ...
    ]
  }, ...
]

```

2.4 G2A self-assessment

Specific access will be provided to CAV services providers and CAV product developers through a self-assessment exercise making use of Cross Skill®. This is a technology-based competency assessment tool that automatically generates assessments from job descriptions or competency profiles. The G2A toolbox front-end will assess the current proficiency level of these users on different CAV related subjects to provide them a personalized list of “recommendations”.

A random set of questions will assess the user’s self-declared competency proficiency (e.g., “I have a limited knowledge of”) and his interest according to dimensions 2 to 6, in order to recommend contents. Cross Skill will only be dedicated to the CAV service and hardware providers target group:

- Carsharing operators
- Driving schools
- Public transport operators
- Ambulance service providers
- Drone operators

Compared to the toolbox free browse or the chatbot, Cross Skill is “competency-centred”. Therefore, each content of the G2A will have to be ranked in terms of “difficulty” or competency proficiency of the targeted visitor (according to its target group):

- proficiency from level 1. Beginner to level 3. Expert.
- a content - e.g. a national regulation report - might be ranked as a 1 (easy to read/understand/use) for a Public transport operator. Meanwhile it might be ranked as a level 3 for a Service provider.

The G2A toolbox front-end offers the option to service providers to use the Cross Skill® system to assess their current proficiency level on different CAV related subjects to obtain a personalized list of “recommendations”.

The Cross Skill® system will be loosely coupled with the G2A toolbox. The toolbox is expected to include a link (see Figure 2-6) that will redirect the user to the Cross Skill® questionnaire (see **Error! Reference source not**

found..7).

Figure 2-6 Potential Mockup of the G2A Toolbox website. In yellow, a button redirecting to the Cross Skill® web page.

Figure 2-7 Potential Mockup of the Cross Skill® web page to which the user gets redirected.

Once the user has completed the questionnaire, the system displays a list of recommended recommendations directly within the page. The rendering is performed by the Cross Skill® web page as illustrated in Figure 2-8.

Note: the mock-ups presented here are only meant to illustrate the redirect flow between the Toolbox website and the Cross Skill® platform and do not presage anything about the final look and feel of the two tools. Same goes for the URLs used.

Figure 2-8 Potential Mockup of the Cross Skill® web page displaying a list of recommendations based on the user self-assessment. The Open button (or any other form of link) redirects to the Toolbox page of the recommendation. Note that the URL is just a proposition and that another (sub)-domain will probably be used.

When the user clicks on the link associated to the recommendation, (s)he gets redirected to the recommendation page on the Toolbox website as illustrated in Figure 2-9 .

Figure 2-9 Potential Mockup of a recommendation page in the Toolbox

Figure 2-10 Sequence diagram of the integration of Cross Skill® with the toolbox

Figure 2-10 summarises the process described previously in a sequence diagram.

To generate a personalised list of recommendations, the system developed by LIST will access the complete metadata of the different recommendations published in the toolbox. This will include, among other things, the recommendation ID (or URL), the target user group(s), the impact type(s), related thematic area(s),...

The system will obtain this information dynamically through the WordPress **REST API**.

2.5 G2A recommendations

The G2A will be filled with 100 recommendations. Each of the recommendations will be composed in line with the following structure:

- Title, description, illustration picture and examples
- Meta data of each recommendation will enable mining the recommendations by:
 - Multi-criteria search
 - Chatbot (keywords)
 - By Cross Skills self-assessment questionnaire (level of proficiency of service providers in the key thematic areas).
 - By internet browsers (SEO)

The template for recommendations is provided in the Annex.

Figure 2-11 Taxonomy of recommendations

A recommendation is a *suggestion or proposal as to the best course of action*, focusing on user acceptance and user behaviour in or near a CAV, identifying factors determining overall acceptance and willingness to use.

User-centric, recommendations will target a wide range of G2A user groups, differing with regards to the ways in which they would interact with CAVs, and how their lives, well-being, employment situation, etc. would be affected by CAV usage and dissemination.

An editorial board will be set up that will allow to increase the qualitative representation of each recommendation. Next to writing style and grammar each recommendation will contain several extrinsic as well as intrinsic characteristics as presented in the following figure.

Extrinsic characteristics	Intrinsic characteristics
<p>Relevant</p> <p>Resulting directly from valid experiences Not extrapolating from collected data</p>	<p>Targeted & specific</p> <p>Should trigger action by responsible stakeholders</p> <p>=> Ask yourself which group of stakeholders you are addressing and what they can expect from the implementation of the recommendation.</p>
<p>Justified</p> <p>Answering the research questions tackled Based on validated and documented data</p>	<p>Measurable</p> <p>How to assess whether their implementation had reached its objective</p> <p>=> Express quantifiable expected outcomes</p>
<p>Feasible</p> <p>Easy to implement</p> <p>Taking available human and material resources in into account</p>	<p>Unambiguous</p> <p>Clear, understandable in only one way</p> <p>=> Use simple and precise language, => Avoid technical terms and jargon</p>

Figure 2-12 Extrinsic and intrinsic characteristics

When writing a recommendation, authors will be asked to direct their recommendation to the specific G2A user group interest. Recommendations are *suggestions or proposals as to the best course of action*, focusing. They should:

- Give direct instructions,
- Be written to relate directly to awareness and user acceptance of CAV,
- Be short, concise and easy to understand,
- highlight the significance or usefulness of the findings.

3 G2A target groups

Among the stakeholders of the CAV ecosystem, the G2A will address five types of users:

Figure 3-1 G2A target groups

The G2A will provide specifically recommendations and guidelines to these five groups of users. These should allow them to raise awareness and user acceptance of CAV.

- Service providers in the field of CAVs and related services,
- Public authorities, local, national or European,
- Researchers, scientists and academics,
- Product developers, producing hardware and/or software,
- Citizen representatives, especially representing Vulnerable Road Users.

Each of the different G2A target groups are shortly present in the following paragraphs.

3.1 Public authorities

CAVs come in the framework of smart mobility, which has increased dramatically in the contemporary transport policy discourse and become a real issue for public authorities with a formal responsibility in the transport system [1]. It is assumed that digital technology will make the

transport sector more resource-efficient and will contribute to the development of sustainable cities and regions [2][3]. Yet, the current window of opportunities towards smart mobility results in a change in the transport planning landscape [4] and a shift in the role of public authorities in the transition to smart and sustainable mobility.

European, national and local public authorities need to rethink their role and governance strategy to find the right balance between leadership, enablement and laissez-faire to ensure that digitalised mobility contributes to their political programs and vision, especially in terms of equity and sustainability [5].

Local authorities deal with more pragmatic issues related to smart and sustainable mobility: they have an important role, not only in implementing political decisions, but also in actively contributing to governance and planning strategies in close collaboration with leading politicians [6].

The European Commission Directorate-General for Mobility and transport “DG MOVE” develops and carries out the Commission’s policies on transport. DG MOVE aims at promoting an efficient and environment friendly mobility. Through the Intelligent Transport Systems Directorate (Connected and Automated Driving (CAD), the European Commission established a new European Partnership on Cooperative, Connected and Automated Mobility under Horizon Europe. The partnership aims to align better public and private efforts through a common and long-term R&I agenda. It will accelerate the implementation of smart, innovative and sustainable mobility solutions for all [7].

3.2 Citizen representative organisations

Citizen representatives are NGOs or associations representing the interests of citizens, including vulnerable citizens.

Vulnerable Road Users (VRU) are defined in the ITS Directive as “non-motorised road users, such as pedestrians and cyclists as well as motorcyclists and persons with disabilities or reduced mobility and orientation”[8].

Following the EC Mobility and transport recommendations, we consider VRU well-being in the deployment of CAVs, striving to accelerate beneficial consequences and to mitigate potential negative effects.

The term ‘vulnerable road user’ is applied to those most at risk in traffic, that is, those unprotected by an external shield [9]. Pedestrians, pedal cyclists and motorcyclists are considered vulnerable road users (VRUs), as they are prone to injury in any vehicular collision, primarily because there is little or no external protective device that could absorb the impact of a road crash. The kinetic forces resulting from differences in the mass and speed of various types of vehicles largely determine the severity of a road crash [10]. According to the latest global assessment of road safety, the World Health Organization (WHO) indicates that vulnerable road users account for more than half of all road fatalities [11] [12].

Different types of vulnerable road users: pedestrians, cyclists, motorcyclists, disabled pedestrians and children.

3.3 Researchers

Research is the systematic process of the collection and analysis of data and information, in order to generate new knowledge, to answer a specific question or to test a hypothesis. Its methodology must be sufficiently documented to permit assessment and replication. Technology is the application of scientific knowledge for practical purposes.

All typologies of science are involved in CAVs from theoretical¹ research to applied/operational research² and methodical and analytical tools development. All strategies of research be they quantitative³, qualitative⁴

¹ Type of research undertaken to advance conceptual understandings.

² Type of research that is undertaken to define solutions to specific problems through proofing in real world conditions.

³ A research strategy which emphasises quantification in the collection and analysis of data. It allows the development or testing of a theory composed of variables, measured with numbers, and analysed with statistical processes to determine the relevant relationships among them. Often used to research social and developmental issues that require large data-sets that cannot be analysed validly or reliably using a qualitative research strategy.

⁴ A research strategy in which data is explored in non-numeric formats, including text, audio, imagery etc. Normally undertaken to gain insights concerning attitudes, beliefs, motivations and behaviours of individuals in relation to social or human problems. It tends to be a strategy associated with inductive reasoning, as well as constructivism and interpretivist approaches to research questions. Its results are not usually considered generalizable, but are often transferable.

or mixed⁵ are involved in CAVs [13]. Some physics research areas are of particular interest for CAVs:

- Autonomous operations (guidance and vision, aerospace mechanics and materials, Unmanned aerial vehicles),
- Data processing and management (Artificial intelligence, neural networks, machine learning),
- Sensor Network technologies (Sensors, signal processing, environmental processing),
- Wireless connectivity,
- Cybersecurity,
- Software engineering and computational languages,
- Road and Vehicles safety (infrastructures).

Social science examines social and behavioral questions associated with CAVs. Looking at CAVs in a holistic approach, social sciences can tackle questions of how culture, social norms, habits and human responses affect how we interact with CAV, questions of governance, economics, ethics, and equity.

3.4 CAV service providers and product developers

Mobility and logistics service providers play a cross cutting role, with activities ranging from challenge definition based on their activity chain needs, via CAV use case development to piloting. When thinking about service providers within the PASCAL project this includes actors like mobility and logistics service providers, public transport operators, yet also insurance and maintenance.

Like the research community private industry has a role to play in the advancement of the CAV technology. Together with public authorities they facilitate demonstration activities in cities and regions, drive consistency and interoperability of common solutions whilst ensuring societal needs are met and suitable regulations are established⁶. In terms of CAV product

⁵ A research strategy that combines qualitative and quantitative data collection and/or analysis

⁶ CCAM partnership

developers, the PAsCAL project includes OEMs, their supply industry yet also telecom and ITS industry.

4 Topic categories, impacts and tool types

4.1 CAV topic areas

PAsCAL defined four thematic domains in which change could improve user acceptance and public awareness. These four topics are:

- Strategies for integrating CCAM in present public policies;
- Design of new CCAM infrastructure and technologies;
- User oriented CCAM ICT developments;
- Management of CCAM and stimulating local economy, social inclusion and environmental protection.

1	Public policies
2	Infrastructure and technologies
3	ICT developments
4	Management and local economy

Figure 4-1 Topic areas

The PAsCAL project identified for each of these four topic categories key areas and related common issues and approaches that influence public awareness and user acceptance of CCAM in their specific domain. Each of these key areas are a category in the topic related categorization of the recommendations. The specific thematic domains are described in more detail in deliverable D8.1.

4.2 CAV impact areas

Following the work on impacts in D7.1 several different human and societal impact areas were identified that can be classified as follow:

- Perceptions of individuals (e.g. users, drivers, pilots, cyclists), acceptance of technology and willingness to use CAVs;

- Impact areas related to the specific needs of vulnerable groups (e.g. elderly, impaired, children), including a spatial division between urban and rural areas; and
- wider societal impact areas.

1	Individual level
2	Vulnerable users
3	Macro-level (societal, economic, environmental)

Figure 4-2 Impact areas

Each of these impact areas are used as a categorisation of the PAsCAL recommendations.

4.3 Tool type

A tool in the PAsCAL project is defined an item or implement used to achieve or measure a level of awareness and user acceptance of CAV. A tool can be used in the different research, CAV thematic areas, by the different G2A target groups.

The tool can be any instrument or approach that helps to evaluate the impact of a change, improving our understanding, or providing an opportunity to intervene when necessary. As a result, the following tool types were defined as a discriminating factor for the tools in the PAsCAL G2A. i.e. Software, research method, business model.

1	Software
2	Research method
3	Business model
4	Other

Figure 4-3 Tool type

5 G2A outlook and functionalities

5.1 Specification of the G2A functionalities

The G2A is provided by the following website link: <https://guide2autonomy.eu/>. Users directly visiting the G2A website will see at first the main page with a title of some recommendations. Users can choose on the left if they want to narrow the result set of recommendations by using filters.

Figure 5-1 Overview page of all the recommendations

If users choose a specific recommendation and click on the link, they are directed to the recommendation page, where the recommendation is being described, an example of a good practice is provided and expected outcomes of the recommendation are indicated. In addition, references and useful links are included (see Figure 5-2). Users can save the recommendation as a PDF file.

Description

Example or good practice

Expected outcomes of recommendation

References & useful links

Save as PDF

Figure 5-2 Recommendation page

For the administrative users, a login username/email with a password is provided (see Figure 5-3).

Figure 5-3 Login page of the G2A website

When the admin user is logged in, the user has to click on the PAsCAL project item.

Figure 5-4 Project page

On the project page, admin users can create the recommendations and create filter options, which can later be used by the G2A users to narrow down their choice of recommendation (see Figure 5-5).

Figure 5-5 Recommendation and filter creation overview page

When adding a recommendation, the admin user is forwarded to the creation page of the recommendation.

Figure 5-6 Recommendation creation page (Part 1)

As shown in Figure 5-6, the admin user can fill in the title of the recommendation. If needed, acronyms can be filled in at a later stage. The main text can be filled in in the description box. The user can upload an image, which fits to the recommendation text.

Figure 5-7 Recommendation creation page (Part 2)

On the same page, if the admin user scrolls down, an example or good practice based on the recommendation can be filled in. In addition, the expected outcomes for the recommendation can be added (see Figure 5-7).

Figure 5-8 shows the references and useful links which can be added to the recommendation. Below, admin users can add the questions and the related questions, which help to set up the chatbot. Based on the questions and answers (Q&A), the chatbot can help external users to navigate through the toolbox and find the recommendation they are looking for.

Figure 5-8 Recommendation creation page (Part 3)

Figure 5-9 Recommendation creation page (Part 4)

Figure 5-9 shows the indication of expertise which is needed for the specific recommendation. The admin user has to set the level of expertise for the recommendation. This includes the general required level of expertise, the expertise with public policies, infrastructure and technologies, ICT developments, user interest and local economy. The

level of expertise for these 4 topics and the general expertise can be set as: Novice, Beginner, Proficient, Expert. These levels of expertise help to set up the Cross Skill tool which, based on the questions, can help users to self-assess their competences and to be guided to the right recommendation.

Filters

Targeted user groups

- Product developers
- Service providers
- Researchers
- Public authorities
- Citizens representatives

Expected impact

- Individual level
- Vulnerable users
- Macro-level (societal, economic, environmental)

Key topics

- Public policies
- Infrastructure and technologies
- ICT developments
- Management and local economy

Type of tool

- Software
- Research method
- Business model
- Other

Source of recommendation

- Project finding
- Other project
- Benchmark/watch

Figure 5-10 Filters to be set for each recommendation

For each recommendation, filters can be set, which will help users to find the recommendations they are looking for. The filters include: targeted user groups (product developers, service providers, researchers, public authorities, citizens representatives), expected impact (on individual or macro-level and vulnerable users), Key topics (public policies,

infrastructure and technologies, ICT developments, management and local economy), type of tool (software, research method, business model, other) and the source of recommendation (project finding, other project, benchmark/watch).

5.2 Next steps

Partners involved in WP8 are asked to provide in total 100 recommendations/guidelines in the following months. Therefore, a workshop with all the involved WP partners is organised end of November 2021 to present the recommendation template and to train them on how to write recommendations/guidelines. Each WP8 task leader is asked to coordinate the writing of approximately 25 recommendations within the frame of their key area in cooperation with the other PASCAL partners. In addition to this, external stakeholders are invited to provide recommendations, which will be included in the G2A. This can be partners from the sister projects, public stakeholders, experts in the field of CAVs etc. Partners are asked to fill in a recommendation template (word document) provided by LuxMobility/LIST.

6 References

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Annex: Recommendations template

Part 1
Title of recommendation
Picture/illustration
Formats: jpeg, ... / Size / weight-definition
Description
Describe recommendation in 200 words max / 3 paragraphs
Example or good practice
Expected outcomes of recommendation
References & useful links

Part 2: Categorisation & tagging		
Target audience		
<p><i>Who is this recommendation addressing?</i> <i>Tick if relevant for each target group</i></p>		
User group	Refine user group if necessary	Relevant for this User group?
Citizens representatives		Yes/no
Public Authorities		Yes/No
Service providers		Yes/no
Researchers		Yes/no
Expected impact	Yes/No	Describe the expected impact
Describe expected impact at individual level	Yes/No	
Describe expected impact for Vulnerable Road Users	Yes/No	
Describe expected impact at macro level (societal, economic, environmental)	Yes:No	
Key thematic area		

Quote the level of expertise required for this content (only for service providers)

	<i>Novice</i>
	<i>Beginner</i>
	<i>Proficient</i>
	<i>expert</i>

Key thematic area	CAV Infrastructure & Legislation	CCAM digital infrastructure	CAV services	In-vehicle development	CAVs and local economy, networks, social inclusion and sustainability
Level of proficiency					
Type of Tool					
software	Research method	Business model	Other:...		
Source of recommendation					
Project finding		Other project	Benchmark/watch		
Key words:					

Part 3: Abbreviations & Glossary	
Acronym	Meaning
xxx	xxx
Vocabulary	
Term/word	Definition/description
Other (please describe)	

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